

Original Research

Financial Reporting Quality on the Cost of Debt with Emphasis on the Role of Financial Constraints in Iran

Mohsen Imeni¹ and Mozhdeh Parvizi

Department of Accounting, Ayandegan Institute of Higher Education,
Tonekabon, Iran

Received 4 June 2025 Revised 16 September 2025 Accepted 21 September 2025
Published 1 March 2026

Abstract

This study examines the relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange, as well as the moderating role of financial constraints in this relationship. The main objective of the study is to identify the effect of financial reporting quality on the cost of debt and evaluate the role of financial constraints as a moderating variable. The present study utilized data from 114 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange from 2015 to 2023, and statistical analyses were conducted using the Panel Data method. Financial constraints were measured with three Altman Z-Score indices and two SA indices (SA1 and SA2). The results indicate that financial reporting quality has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the cost of debt. Therefore, the research hypothesis that the cost of debt decreases with the increase in financial reporting quality was not confirmed. Also, the moderating effect of financial constraints on the relationship between financial reporting quality and cost of debt was not significant with any of the Z, SA1, and SA2 indices. By focusing on the Iranian market and using several indicators of financial constraints simultaneously, this study fills the gap in the international literature on the moderating effect of financial constraints on the relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt. It provides local empirical evidence for financial decision-makers and policymakers.

Keywords: Cost of debt, financial constraints, financial reporting quality, information asymmetry, Z-index.

¹ Corresponding author's email: imeni@aihe.ac.ir

Introduction

Accounting information is a valuable and essential source for decision-making by contracting parties and is a key tool in assessing the accountability of managers. High-quality financial reporting can increase investment efficiency and reduce information asymmetry (Biddle et al., 2009). The existence of information asymmetry has consequences, including adverse selection and moral hazard. In adverse selection conditions, managers may allocate financial resources inefficiently to inappropriate projects, resulting in increased investor expectations, higher investment risk, and ultimately, increased financing costs (Saghafi & Arabmazar Yazdi, 2010). In contrast, high-quality financial reporting strengthens the supervisory power of shareholders and owners over managers' investment decisions and reduces the risks of bias and moral hazard (Ahmad et al., 2023; Al-Hiyari et al., 2024; Ayagi & Salisu, 2023).

As a key dimension of information transparency, the quality of financial reporting plays an important role in reducing information asymmetry among managers, investors, and creditors. By increasing the reliability and timeliness of information, high-quality financial reporting enables creditors to assess the risk of default more accurately and enhances their confidence in the company's financial statements (Biddle et al., 2009; Ahmad et al., 2023). In such circumstances, the possibility of agency problems such as bias and moral hazard is reduced, and the decision-making process of creditors in granting financial facilities is improved (Ayagi & Salisu, 2023). Therefore, it can be expected that companies with higher financial reporting quality have access to cheaper sources of finance and more favorable credit agreements. From the perspective of the cost of financing, the quality of financial reporting directly affects the cost of debt. Transparent financial statements allow for a more accurate assessment of the company's repayment capacity and reduce the perceived risk of creditors; as a result, interest rates and other costs related to debt in such companies will be lower (Francis et al., 2005; Beatty et al., 2010). In contrast, poor reporting increases uncertainty, making it challenging to assess credit risk, and ultimately leads creditors to demand higher risk premiums (Abad et al., 2017; Nikolov et al., 2021). In other words, high-quality financial reporting not only helps reduce the cost of debt but also facilitates stable access to long-term financing. However, the level of information asymmetry affects the maturity structure of debt: companies with high information asymmetry (poor reporting) rely more on short-term debt, while companies with higher transparency (high-quality reporting) tend to lean towards long-term debt (Van et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2025).

Financial constraints, measured in this study by indicators such as Altman's Z-Score, are one of the most significant challenges for companies (Kurt, 2018). Financially constrained companies either face high costs of external financing or do not have access to these resources at all. In the absence of sufficient internal resources, it becomes difficult to make optimal investment decisions (Armstrong et al., 2019). In other words, companies that face lower free cash flows tend to have lower free cash flows. As a result, managerial tendencies towards empire building (Jensen, 1986) are less evident. These companies, as highlighted in the work of Grossman and Hart (1986) and Hovakimian (2011), consider a more cautious approach to project selection and investment to be necessary. Managers working in this field are well aware that the continuous erosion of firm value can increase their vulnerability to employment risk. This is particularly important in the Iranian capital

market, which is characterized by limited transparency, a weak credit rating system, and widespread information asymmetry (Rahban et al., 2024). Structural weaknesses, combined with economic volatility and severe restrictions on access to external resources, have significantly increased the financing costs, and especially the cost of debt, of Iranian firms (Tuğsal Doruk & Martial Gohore, 2024). Despite the importance of this issue, most previous research has only examined the direct effect of financial reporting quality on the cost of capital or the cost of debt (Francis et al., 2005; Biddle & Hilary, 2006; Verdi, 2006; Beatty et al., 2010). In recent years, some studies have shown that financial constraints can affect the intensity and direction of financial relationships (Valta, 2012; Chen et al., 2020; Hou et al., 2023), but there is little evidence on the moderating role of financial constraints in the relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt. This gap in the literature is particularly pronounced in emerging markets such as Iran, where credit risks and structural financing constraints are more severe. Therefore, this study helps to fill this gap theoretically by developing a framework of agency and information asymmetry in the form of a moderation model, and practically by providing local evidence from the Iranian market.

The findings of this study are important from both a scientific and practical perspective, even though none of the research hypotheses were confirmed. In the financial and accounting literature, numerous studies have demonstrated that the quality of financial reporting is associated with a reduction in the cost of debt, and that financial constraints can either strengthen or weaken this relationship. However, the results from the Iranian capital market contradicted this evidence. They showed that neither the quality of financial reporting nor financial constraints has a significant effect on the cost of debt. This discrepancy with theoretical expectations and international evidence is itself considered a scientific innovation because it indicates that existing theories cannot be fully generalized to all environments. The second innovation of the study is its focus on the specific institutional context of Iran. The bank-based structure of financing, the extensive reliance of banks on collateral, the weakness of the credit rating system, and the low quality of corporate governance are among the factors that can cause the quality of financial reporting not to affect the cost of debt in practice. This study provides the first empirical evidence that, in such an environment, financial reporting alone does not function similarly to that in developed markets and cannot be the primary tool for managing the cost of capital.

From a scientific perspective, the rejection of the hypotheses reveals a new research gap. This finding clarifies the path for further research to examine other institutional and economic factors that affect the cost of debt in Iran, including banking relationships, credit policies, types of company ownership, and audit quality. Therefore, the present study not only challenges the existing literature but also provides a basis for developing indigenous theoretical frameworks on the relationship between financial reporting and the cost of debt in emerging markets.

From a practical perspective, the innovation of the study lies in conveying a clear message to policymakers and regulatory agencies: improving the quality of financial reporting alone is insufficient to reduce the cost of debt. Complementary institutional reforms, such as enhancing the bank credit rating system, mandating the disclosure of real financial risks, and improving audit quality, should be pursued simultaneously so that

financial reporting can effectively play its role in reducing information asymmetry. Thus, rather than repeating well-known results, the present study presents a different picture of the realities of the Iranian market that has both scientific value and important policy implications.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature and develops the research hypotheses. Section 3 presents the research methodology, data, and variables. Section 4 reports the empirical results, and Section 5 discusses the findings and practical implications. Section 6 concludes with recommendations and suggestions for future research.

Literature

Effect of Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ) on Cost of Debt (CoD)

One of the main reasons for the failure of companies is their lack of adequate investment and inappropriate and inadequate financial security. For example, owners of such companies may choose an improper mix of resources (debt versus equity), or they may raise resources that impose high liquidity constraints on them, or they may enter into agreements that impose high-cost commitments on them (Ebrahimi, 2022; Vihriälä, 2023; Bracht et al., 2024). They may even turn to resource providers for financing that are difficult to work with. Therefore, existing weaknesses lead to inappropriate investment that threatens the survival and life of the company (Cassar, 2004). In addition, an inappropriate capital structure for any company affects all areas of a company's activity. It can cause problems such as inefficiency in product marketing, inability to utilize human resources properly, and similar matters (Neville & Lucey, 2022). Companies' financial statements should provide information that is useful to potential and actual investors, lenders, and other users in making sound investment, credit, and similar decisions. Financial statements should provide the information necessary to assess the financial position and economic basis of the institution, assess its performance and profitability, assess how it has secured its finances and spent its cash, assess how it has discharged its direct management responsibilities and fulfilled its legal obligations, and provide information. Financial reports are of particular importance for better understanding the financial information provided and also for helping to make future predictions (Zhou et al., 2021; Biehl et al., 2024). Therefore, these reports play a fundamental role in achieving organizational goals, and improving their quality can lead to improving the investment efficiency of companies as well as maintaining and developing their resources (Martiny et al., 2024). Recent findings show that improving the level of financial reporting has important economic consequences, including increasing investment efficiency (Healy & Palepu, 2001; Bushman & Smith, 2001; Lambert et al., 2007). According to Gao and Zhu (2015), the positive relationship between information asymmetry and market financial leverage is due to the difference in the competitive costs of different types of external financing, which is affected by the degree of information asymmetry—the more severe the adverse selection problem, the higher the cost of equity. Firms with high levels of information asymmetry tend to use more debt to avoid the high agency costs of equity capital (Morellec & Schürhoff, 2011). Barclay and Smith (1995) also argue that the negative relationship between information asymmetry and debt maturity is because the pricing of long-term debt is more sensitive to information asymmetry than short-term

debt; hence, long-term debt is associated with a higher information cost. Therefore, firms with high information asymmetry (low FRQ) tend to rely on short-term debt. In contrast, firms with lower information asymmetry (higher FRQ) tend to use long-term debt (Flannery, 1986). In this context, the present study seeks to examine the relationship between FRQ and the cost of debt for firms.

Role of transparency in emerging markets

Low transparency in financial information means preventing access to data, presenting inaccurate or distorted information, or the market's inability to ensure the adequacy, relevance, and quality of information (Ajina et al., 2015). In order to gain investor confidence in the capital market, companies need to increase transparency in providing information. Investors rely on information published by listed companies. They need reliable, timely, and understandable information that is easy to analyze. In fact, information transparency is an indicator of management performance in providing important and necessary information in a correct, clear, timely, and accessible manner. This indicator reflects whether investors have an accurate picture of what is happening inside the company (Roszkowska-Menkes et al., 2024). The purpose of information transparency is to help assess the quality, financial performance, financial position, and financial flexibility of the business unit (Abed et al., 2024). In other words, financial information transparency affects the quality of investment decisions (Huong Dau et al., 2024). Adequate disclosure of information by economic figures helps investors and creditors in searching for investment opportunities. Thus, capital is directed to the most efficient companies so that financing through investment is carried out correctly. Bushman and Smith (2003) defined corporate transparency as the widespread availability of reliable and relevant information about the outcomes of investment opportunities, periodic performance, financial condition, corporate governance, value, and risk-taking of publicly traded companies. Research on the quality of accounting information suggests that high-quality accounting reporting can improve investment efficiency by reducing information asymmetry between managers and shareholders (Healy & Palepu, 2001). Accordingly, high-quality reporting allows companies with limited financial resources to raise more capital from investors and avoid the problem of underinvestment. Furthermore, improving the quality of accounting reporting can reduce managers' incentives to overinvest through increased monitoring or better contracts (Biddle et al., 2009). On the one hand, transparency assures small shareholders that they will always have access to timely and reliable information about the company's value. On the other hand, it encourages managers to pay more attention to short-term benefits than to truly enhance the company's value (Mohammadi & Moein Nezhad, 2015). Transparency of information required by the capital market can affect market efficiency and the added value of companies in three ways: first, by providing reliable and useful information about the results of investment opportunities with lower risk, second, by guiding managers in the optimal allocation and use of resources in investment opportunities that have appropriate returns, and finally, by reducing information asymmetry between managers and major shareholders on the one hand and minority shareholders on the other. Understanding the economic consequences of a company's information environment (information transparency) is an important topic in accounting research.

Hypothesis Development

According to agency theory, conflicts of interest between managers and shareholders lead to agency costs. Low-quality financial reporting exacerbates this conflict and increases information asymmetry between managers and investors (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). In conditions of information asymmetry, investors and creditors cannot properly assess the true risk of the company, so to compensate for the unknown risk, they demand a higher risk premium, which is reflected in the form of increased interest rates and the cost of debt. In contrast, high-quality financial reporting increases transparency, reduces the problems of adverse selection and malfeasance, and leads to a decrease in the cost of debt (Biddle et al., 2009; Francis et al., 2005). Research shows that the FRQ—often proxied by accrual quality—can positively influence lenders' decisions, thereby reducing the CoD financing (Acheh & Gallali, 2015; Vander Bauwhede et al., 2015; Ahmed et al., 2002). According to agency theory, higher-quality reports reduce information asymmetry between managers and lenders, lowering agency costs and perceived lending risk.

From the perspective of signaling theory, transparent and reliable reports serve as positive signals to creditors regarding the firm's financial health. In contrast, low-quality reporting distorts investment decisions, increases information risk, and raises the cost of capital (Leuz & Verrecchia, 2005). Financial transparency demonstrates to creditors that the company has good liquidity and financial stability, which tends to reduce moral hazard. This signal increases creditor confidence and, as a result, more favorable financing conditions (Beatty et al., 2010). In contrast, poor or ambiguous reporting sends a negative signal to the market and increases doubts about the ability to repay debt, which leads to higher interest rates and tighter credit conditions. Several studies have confirmed the negative relationship between the quality of financial reporting and the cost of debt. Francis et al. (2005) showed that higher earnings quality reduces the cost of capital and debt. Beatty et al. (2010) and Verdi (2006) also reported that more transparent reporting reduces the perceived risk of creditors and, as a result, lowers interest rates. Also, Abad et al. (2017) and Nikolov et al. (2021) showed that in markets with more severe information asymmetry, the effect of financial reporting quality on the cost of debt is stronger. These findings suggest that financial reporting transparency not only enhances access to finance but also reduces its associated costs.

Empirical evidence supports this view. Ding et al. (2016) showed that high-quality earnings improve access to debt financing and reduce borrowing costs. In emerging markets, where external financing—especially bank loans—remains the dominant funding source (Beck et al., 2008), this effect can be more pronounced due to weaker credit assessment systems and less stringent reporting regulations. In Iran, limited transparency, underdeveloped credit assessment systems, and widespread information asymmetry (Rahban et al., 2024) underscore the importance of high-quality reporting in reducing financing costs. Based on these arguments, this study expects that Iranian firms with higher FRQ will face lower debt financing costs. In summary, based on the theoretical foundations of agency and signaling and empirical evidence, higher quality financial reporting is expected to increase creditor confidence by reducing information and agency problems. This confidence is manifested in the form of lower interest rates, easier credit terms, and a reduction in the cost of debt. Therefore, the first hypothesis of the study (H1) is stated as follows:

H₁: There is a negative relationship between FRQ and the CoD.

Financial constraint (FC) refers to a situation in which firms have difficulty accessing external financing or their financing costs are higher than optimal (Fazzari et al., 1988). In such situations, even profitable projects may not be implemented due to a lack of internal financing or high borrowing rates. This issue is rooted in the theory of asymmetric information and agency problems (Le et al., 2021; Nikolov et al., 2021; Figueroa et al., 2023). When a firm's information is incomplete or opaque, investors and lenders are more cautious and raise the cost of financing. Thus, FC not only limits the firm's ability to invest but also increases the risk of default and, consequently, the cost of debt (Kaplan & Zingales, 1997). The financial constraint literature has provided several measures of FC over the past decades. Altman's Z-Score (Altman, 1968) is based on financial ratios and is widely used to predict bankruptcy and measure the ability to survive. SA indices (Hadlock & Pierce, 2010) also emphasize the structural and external factors that affect financial constraints, focusing on the size and age of the firm. Using multiple indices (Z, SA1, SA2) simultaneously can provide a more comprehensive picture of the financial constraints of firms, as each one emphasizes a different dimension (bankruptcy risk, structure, or liquidity constraints). Previous studies have shown that financial constraints have a significant impact on investment decisions and the financing structure of firms. For example, Almeida et al. (2004) showed that financially constrained firms allocate a higher proportion of their internal cash flows to investment. Also, Valta (2012) and Chen et al. (2022) show that FC affects not only the level of investment but also the cost of debt, as lenders charge higher interest rates and stricter terms to firms with limited financial resources. In other words, FC increases credit risk and demands a risk premium from creditors.

Ding et al.'s (2016) study, examining data from private Chinese companies, shows that higher FRQ not only reduces the CoD but also increases access to debt resources. Using the earnings quality index as a proxy for FRQ, the authors find that this effect is much stronger in regions that are less institutionally and economically developed (based on the NERI index). This finding implies that in environments with weaker financial and credit infrastructure—which can be considered similar to the situation of highly financially constrained companies—creditors are more dependent on transparent and reliable financial information. As a result, FRQ plays a more important role in reducing the cost of debt financing. Accordingly, the results of Ding et al. (2016) provide strong evidence in support of the view that the impact of FRQ on the CoD increases under conditions of more severe FC. This is consistent with the logic of the second hypothesis, which expects the negative relationship between FRQ and CoD to be stronger in firms with greater FC.

In emerging markets such as Iran, financial constraints are more severe than in developed markets, as weak financial institutions, a lack of efficient credit rating systems, and low transparency exacerbate the problem of access to finance. Therefore, in such environments, the moderating role of FC in the relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt is expected to be more prominent. Examining this role can not only fill the gap in the international literature but also provide valuable local evidence for policymakers and financial managers. Under such conditions, creditors may scrutinize financial statements more closely, making FRQ's effect on debt cost stronger. This is particularly relevant in Iran, where macroeconomic volatility and structural weaknesses

intensify financing challenges (Shemshad & Imeni, 2022). Therefore, the second hypothesis is:

H₂: A higher FRQ leads to a reduction in the cost of debt, and this relationship is stronger in companies with greater financial constraint.

Research Method

The study's purpose is applied. The inference method is descriptive-correlational. The research design is post-event. The purpose of the study is applied. The inference method is descriptive-correlational. Since the financial data of the companies is needed to examine the research hypotheses, and this information has been prepared in the past, the research design is post-event.

Population and Statistical Sample

The statistical population of this study includes companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange during the period from the beginning of 2015 to the end of 2023, a period of 9 years. Since the JCPOA agreement was signed in 2015, Iran has implemented International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to attract foreign investors, including the standard related to the statement of cash flows. Accordingly, the research period was selected from 2015 to 2023, which is the last fiscal year available for data collection. In addition, in order to standardize the research sample, certain conditions were considered, which are explained below.

1. The companies did not change their fiscal year during the research period.
2. Due to differences in the activities of investment, financial intermediation, holding, banking, and leasing companies, these companies were excluded from the sample.
3. They were listed on the Stock Exchange before 2015 and were active during the research period.
4. To increase comparability, the companies' fiscal year ends at the end of 12/29/XX.

After applying these restrictions, 114 companies were selected as a statistical sample over a nine-year research period (number of observations: 1,026 company-years).

Experimental Model and Variables

In this study, a panel data regression model was employed to test the hypotheses. The basic regression model presented by Van et al. (2022) was also employed to test these hypotheses.

$$CoD_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FRQ_{it} + \beta_2 AUD_{it} + \beta_3 OWN_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Dependent variable: Cost of Debt (CoD): obtained by dividing financial expenses (interest expenses) by total debt (long-term + short-term debt) (Vander Bauwhede et al., 2015).

Independent variable: According to Amrah and Hashim (2020), this study will use the Kothari et al. (2005) model as a criterion for measuring the FRQ.

$$\frac{TA_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = a_0 + a_1 \left[\frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} \right] + a_2 \left[\frac{\Delta REV_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} - \frac{\Delta REC_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} \right] + a_3 \left[\frac{PPE_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} \right] + a_4 \left(\frac{NI_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} \right) + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

In the model, total accruals (TA) represent the difference between operating profit and operating cash flow. ΔREV Current year revenue changes from the previous year, and ΔREC changes in accounts receivable are represented, as are property, plant, and equipment. NI represents net income, and A represents total assets. i, t represents company i and year t for a particular company. The residuals of the model are represented by ε . Residuals from the regression model are used to substitute for discretionary accruals. In line with Hope et al. (2013) and Khan et al. (2024), our tests use absolute values of discretionary accruals as a proxy for FRQ. The absolute values of discretionary accruals are multiplied by -1 so that higher values of discretionary accruals indicate higher FRQ.

Moderator variable: Financial constraint (FC): In this study, the following three indicators are used to represent the company's financial constraints: (Z, SA1, SA2). Model 2 is the main model, with each of the three proposed indicators substituted for FC during testing.

$$COD_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FRQ_{it} + \beta_2 FC_{it} + \beta_3 FC_{it} * FRQ_{it} + \beta_4 AUD_{it} + \beta_5 S - OWN_{it} + \beta_6 SIZE_{it} + \beta_7 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

According to a study by Van et al. (2022), Z-Altman's modified criterion has been used to calculate financial constraints in financial statements:

$$Z = 1.2X_1 + 1.4X_2 + 3.3X_3 + 0.6X_4 + 1.0X_5$$

X_1 : The ratio of working capital to total assets; X_2 : The ratio of retained earnings to total assets; X_3 : The ratio of earnings before interest and taxes to total assets; X_4 : The Ratio of the book value of debts to the market value of equity; X_5 : Total assets/sales ratio. If the Z-score is less than 1.81, financial constraints are increasing; in this case, the number is one. Otherwise, the number is zero.

The SA index was proposed by Hadlock and Pierce (2010). It demonstrates that external factors are important in measuring a company's financial constraints. The SA index takes into account the size and age of the company. Companies with fewer constraints have a high SA score, and the opposite is true for companies with more financial constraints. In the SA index, company size is measured by taking the natural logarithm of total assets or sales. A company's age is calculated from the date it was listed on the stock exchange. After calculating each variable, the median of the numbers is then calculated, and the numbers above it will be one; otherwise, they will be zero.

$$SA1 = -0.737Assets + 0.0434Assets^2 - 0.040Age$$

$$SA2 = -0.737Sale + 0.0434Sale^2 - 0.040Age$$

In this study, three different indices (Z, SA1, and SA2) were used to measure financial constraint, because no single index is able to provide a comprehensive picture of the financial constraint status of companies. The Z index, introduced by Altman, relies on financial ratios and accounting information and mainly indicates the company's ability to continue operating and the risk of bankruptcy. In contrast, the SA index, introduced by Hadlock and Pierce (2010), focuses on structural and external factors such as the size and age of the company and can be calculated from both the perspective of assets (SA1) and sales (SA2). For this reason, using these indices simultaneously reduces the error caused by choosing a single measure and increases the validity of the results. One of the notable findings of the present study is the significant difference in the results of the Z index and the two SA indices. This difference is due to the distinct nature of the indices; Thus, a company may be in a favorable financial position (high Z) but still face structural financial constraints (high SA) due to being small or new. This distinction shows that using a combination of various indicators can provide a more complete picture of the financial constraints of companies, especially in emerging and risky markets such as Iran.

Control variables: In order to control for the effect of other factors on the relationship between FRQ and cost of debt, the following four control variables were selected based on previous studies:

Firm size (Size): Firm size affects access to debt markets and financing conditions. Larger firms usually have scale advantages, income diversification, and higher creditworthiness with creditors, which can lead to a lower cost of debt (Rapposelli et al., 2024). The natural logarithm of the book value of total assets measures this variable.

Leverage (Lev): The debt-to-asset ratio indicates the level of financial risk of the firm. Firms with higher leverage tend to have a higher default risk and, as a result, may face a higher cost of debt (Valta, 2012; Cathcart et al., 2020). This variable is obtained by dividing total liabilities by total assets.

Audit firm size (AUD): Audit quality can affect creditors' perceptions of the transparency and reliability of financial information. Companies audited by an audit firm (as the largest government audit firm) tend to have greater credibility with capital markets and lenders (Hou et al., 2023). This variable is defined as a dummy variable that takes the value one if audited by an audit firm and the value zero otherwise.

State Ownership (S-Own): The percentage of state ownership in the shareholding structure can affect perceived risk and access to financial resources. State-owned companies often enjoy implicit government support, which can reduce their cost of debt (Ding et al., 2021; Szarzec et al., 2021). This variable is measured as the percentage of state ownership in a given year.

In order to better understand the theoretical framework and relationships between research variables, the conceptual model is drawn in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Findings

Descriptive Statistics

In this section, we first discuss and examine descriptive statistics indicators, which include central indices (maximum, minimum, and mean) and dispersion indices (standard deviation). Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics results for the quantitative data, while Table 2 shows the statistics for the dummy data.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Symbol	mean	median	Max	Min	S.D
Cost of debt	CoD	0.171	0.15	0.35	0.12	0.082
Financial reporting quality	FRQ	-0.087	-0.06	-0.86	-0.0001	0.09
State ownership	S-Own	0.32	0.21	0.78	0.01	0.32
Firm size	SIZE	14.52	14.42	20.46	10.16	1.61
Debt ratio	LEV	0.62	0.60	3.97	0.046	0.37

Table 2. Dummy variable

Variable		Number	Percentage (%)
Financial Constraint (Z-Altman)	(0)	972	77.51
	(1)	282	22.49
Financial Constraint (SA1) Assets	(0)	463	36.93
	(1)	791	63.07
Financial Constraint (SA2) Sales	(0)	532	42.42
	(1)	722	57.57
Audit Size	(0)	989	78.87
	(1)	265	21.13

Based on the results of Table 1, the mean CoD of 17 percent indicates that a significant portion of the companies' resources is financed at relatively high rates. The standard deviation of 0.082 for this variable indicates a significant difference between companies in terms of the CoD. The FRQ, with an average of 0.087 and a relatively high standard deviation (0.09), indicates that the dispersion of reporting quality among companies is high, and some companies have very weak or very strong reporting. The debt ratio, with

an average of 0.62, indicates the high dependence of companies on debt financing, and even the maximum values (3.97) indicate very high financial leverage in some companies. State ownership with a mean of 32 percent indicates a significant role of the government in the ownership structure of companies in this sample, which is relatively high and in line with the characteristics of the Iranian capital market. According to Table 2, in Altman's Z index, 77.5% of the companies are in a state without financial constraints ($Z \geq 1.81$), which indicates the relative financial health of the majority of the sample. However, based on the SA1 (assets) and SA2 (sales) indices, a higher percentage of companies are identified as having financial constraints (63.07% and 57.57%, respectively), which indicates that structural measures reveal more constraints in the Iranian capital market than traditional financial measures. Also, only 21.13% of the companies have been audited by the Audit Organization, which could indicate the lower share of government audits among listed companies.

Regression Model Test

Before estimating the model, it is necessary to perform related tests. The type of model is determined using the F-Limer test. If the p-value is less than 5 percent, the panel method will be used for estimation. According to Table 3, the significance level of the F-Limer test in the regression models of this study is reported to be less than 0.05; therefore, hypothesis H1 (panel model) is confirmed. After ensuring the difference in width from the origin between years, the next step is to select the appropriate estimation method (fixed or random effects). For this purpose, the Hausman test is used. The F-Limer test determines whether the data should be analyzed as pooled or a panel. The results of this test (significance level less than 5 percent) showed that the panel model is more appropriate. Then, the Hausman test was performed to select between fixed and random effects. The significance of the results ($p < 0.05$) indicates that the fixed-effects model is superior because it controls for unobserved heterogeneities among firms and makes the results more reliable based on the specific characteristics of each firm.

Table 3. Model test

Model Title	F-Limer	p-value	Test result
Base Model	19.45	0.0000	Null hypothesis confirmed - Panel model
Model - Z	20.47	0.0000	Null hypothesis confirmed - Panel model
Model - SA1	19.308	0.0000	Null hypothesis confirmed - Panel model
Model - SA2	19.707	0.0000	Null hypothesis confirmed - Panel model.

Table 4. Hausman test results

Model Title	χ^2_{stat}	p-value	Test result
Base Model	14.26	0.0123	Panel model with fixed effects
Model - Z	18.55	0.0015	Panel model with fixed effects
Model - SA1	13.22	0.0134	Panel model with fixed effects
Model - SA2	14.88	0.0041	Panel model with fixed effects

According to the Hausman test, the regression models in this study should be fitted using panel data model estimation with the fixed effects method.

Regression Model Estimation

Based on the diagnostic tests explained above and considering that the Limer test indicated panel-type data and variance heterogeneity in the model, the GLS method was used to estimate the model. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Results of the basic model test based on fixed effects

Variable	Coeff.	t-stat.	Sig.
C	0.194	8.13*	0.000
FRQ	0.016	2.11*	0.0344
AUD	0.004	2.59*	0.0095
S-OWN	-0.007	-3.48*	0.0005
SIZE	-0.008	-6.225*	0.000
LEV	0.007	1.216	0.2242
R ²	0.69	R ² _{Adj}	0.66
F	22.19	D-W	1.75

*Significant at the 95% confidence level.

According to Table 5, the significance level between the two variables is 0.034, which is lower than the level of significance considered in the present study (5%). The absolute value of the t-statistic (2.11) is also greater than the critical value of 1.96 for a standard normal distribution of 0.95. Therefore, at a 95% confidence level, there is a positive and significant relationship between the FRQ and the CoD. The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between FRQ and CoD at the 95% confidence level. This finding is contrary to the initial theoretical expectation that high FRQ would reduce the cost of debt. The results indicate that firms with higher-quality financial reporting incur a higher cost of debt in the sample studied. The positive coefficient of auditor size (AUD) indicates that firms audited by an audit firm may face higher debt costs, possibly due to the firm's focus on larger or riskier firms. The non-significance of financial leverage (LEV) could indicate that the debt market in Iran is less sensitive to relative changes in leverage or that other variables absorb this effect.

The second hypothesis was tested using three financial constraint indicators; the results are indicated in Table 6.

According to Table 6, the significance level of the moderating effect variable of FRQ and FC based on the Z index is 0.0246, which is less than the significance level (5%). Also, the t-statistic is 2.35; therefore, at a 95% confidence level, FRQ has a significant effect on the cost of debt, with the moderating role of FC based on the Z index. Also, the significance level of the moderating effect variable of FRQ and FC based on the SA1 index is 0.3056, and the t statistic is 1.02. Therefore, at a 95% confidence level, FRQ does not significantly affect the cost of debt, with the moderating role of FC based on the SA1 index. Also, based on Table 6, the significance level of the SA2 index is 0.077, which is higher than the 5% significance level considered in the present study. Therefore, at a

confidence level of 95%, the FRQ does not significantly affect the cost of debt when FC are taken into account based on the SA2 index. The moderating effect of FRQ*FC shows that in firms with more FC (e.g., Z=1), the relationship between FRQ and the CoD becomes stronger. A summary of the results of this study is presented in Table 7.

Table 6. Result of the hypothesis test with the moderating role of financial constraint indicators

Symbol	Results	Z-Altman	SA1	SA2
C	Coeff.	0.19	0.20	0.18
	t-stat.	8.49*	7.48*	8.02*
	Sig.	0.000	0.000	0.000
FRQ	Coeff.	0.01	0.009	0.004
	t-stat.	2.17*	1.30	0.35
	Sig.	0.0337	0.1914	0.722
FC	Coeff.	0.008	0.006	0.0004
	t-stat.	3.21*	4.16*	0.36
	Sig.	0.0013	0.000	0.7117
FRQ*FC	Coeff.	0.004	0.01	0.36
	t-stat.	2.35*	1.02	1.76
	Sig.	0.0246	0.3056	0.0777
AUD	Coeff.	0.003	0.0003	0.004
	t-stat.	1.72	2.30*	2.36*
	Sig.	0.0853	0.0211	0.018
S-OWN	Coeff.	-0.07	-0.006	-0.007
	t-stat.	-3.35*	-2.95*	-3.39*
	Sig.	0.0008	0.003	0.0007
SIZE	Coeff.	-0.008	-0.009	-0.008
	t-stat.	-6.64*	-5.95*	-6.12*
	Sig.	0.000	0.000	0.000
LEV	Coeff.	0.004	0.006	0.007
	t-stat.	0.80	1.05	1.19
	Sig.	0.4195	0.29	0.231
	R ²	0.70	0.69	0.70
	R ² _{Adj.}	0.67	0.66	0.67
	F	22.75	21.59	22.34
	D-W	1.51	1.56	1.50

*Significant at the 95% confidence level.

Table 7. Summary of the results of the hypotheses

Research hypotheses	Nexus	Results
FRQ affects the CoD.	-	Not accepted
FRQ affects the CoD, with FC playing a moderating role based on the Z-index.	-	Not accepted
FRQ affects the CoD, with FC based on the SA1 index moderating the effect.	-	Not accepted
FRQ affects the CoD, with FC the moderating role of financial constraints based on the SA2 index.	-	Not accepted

Additional tests

The GMM approach was used to examine the endogenous effect of variables, and the results are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. GMM test results.

Variable	Coeff.	t-stat.	Sig.
CoD _{t-1}	0.126	4.55*	0.000
FRQ	1.649	2.52*	0.011
AUD	3.783	3.79*	0.000
S-OWN	2.532	4.17*	0.000
SIZE	-0.743	-1.708	0.087
LEV	0.459	1.376	0.168
J-Stat.	5.69	AR (1)	2.95
Prob.	0.06	AR (2)	0.02

The results in Table 8 show that the instrumental variables used in the model are valid, given that the probability of the J-statistic is greater than the alpha value (5%). The residual correlation test also shows that the disorder sentences have a first-order serial correlation AR (1) but do not have a second-order serial correlation AR (2). Based on this, it can be claimed that the GMM method is an appropriate method for estimating the model. The results of Table 8 showed that the relationship between FRQ and CoD is positive.

Conclusion and Discussion

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of financial reporting quality on the cost of debt and the role of financial constraints as a moderating variable in the Iranian capital market. The results of data analysis showed that, contrary to expectations and research hypotheses, there is a positive and significant relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt. Additionally, examining the role of financial constraints revealed that this variable has no significant impact on the relationship above. It was expected, based on theoretical foundations and international evidence, that a higher quality of financial reporting would be associated with a reduction

in information asymmetry between managers and financiers. As a result, the cost of debt would be reduced. Numerous foreign studies, including those in developed markets, have demonstrated that financial transparency and the provision of high-quality information foster greater trust among investors and creditors, thereby reducing the credit risk associated with economic units. However, the findings of the present study in the Iranian market showed the opposite of this expectation. The existence of a positive relationship between financial reporting quality and the cost of debt could be due to the specific characteristics of the country's financial market. In Iran, the financing structure is primarily bank-oriented, and bank decisions are not necessarily based solely on the quality of financial reports; factors such as institutional relationships, credit policies, collateral, and macroeconomic conditions also play a significant role. In such circumstances, high-quality financial reporting may reveal more information about the real and sometimes risky situation of companies, rather than reducing risk. Therefore, instead of reducing interest rates or the cost of debt, creditors apply higher rates to compensate for the disclosed risks. On the other hand, weaknesses in the implementation of corporate governance principles, concentration of ownership, as well as severe asymmetry between accounting information and economic realities, can be considered factors that prevent the quality of financial reporting in Iran from having a reducing effect on the cost of debt.

The results of the second hypothesis test showed that financial constraints have failed to moderate the relationship between the quality of financial reporting and the cost of debt. This finding suggests that in the Iranian market, decisions regarding the cost of debt are more influenced by macroeconomic factors and banks' credit policies, rather than companies' financial constraints alone, playing a significant role in this process. In other words, whether a company has high financial constraints or not, the quality of financial reporting will have a similar effect on its cost of debt. This issue can be attributed to the specific structure of the Iranian banking system, where non-financial factors, such as organizational connections, government support, and policy considerations, strongly influence the allocation of facilities and financial resources. In contrast, conventional financial and reporting criteria play a lesser role. The results of this study showed that the evidence obtained in the Iranian market differs from the results of many studies conducted in other countries. This difference can be informative for researchers, company managers, and financial policymakers in the country. From a policy perspective, supervisory and regulatory institutions must pay attention to strengthening the role of financial reporting in the credit process so that the quality of financial reporting is used as a tool to reduce ambiguity and improve decision-making, rather than being considered a sign of increased risk. The findings can also convey the message to corporate managers that improving the quality of financial reporting alone will not lead to a reduction in the cost of debt; rather, institutional reforms in the fields of corporate governance, information transparency, and banking policies are necessary to achieve this goal. Finally, this research also has limitations, including focusing on data available in the capital market and a specific time period. It is suggested that future research examine the role of other institutional factors, the quality of corporate governance, and the effects of the macroeconomic environment on the relationship between financial reporting and the cost of debt.

This result is not consistent with the findings of Lee and Richie (2016), Amrah and Hashim (2020), Le et al. (2021), and Van et al. (2022). The primary reason for this

discrepancy can be attributed to the institutional, economic, and structural differences between the Iranian market and the markets examined in previous research. In developed markets, financial systems exhibit stronger information transparency, regulatory efficiency, and corporate governance; therefore, the quality of financial reporting can effectively reduce information asymmetry and lower the cost of debt. However, in Iran, the environmental conditions are such that this mechanism does not function properly. Weaknesses in the bank credit rating system, excessive reliance on collateral instead of relying on financial information, political and institutional considerations in the allocation of credit resources, and the inefficiency of supervisory institutions mean that even high-quality financial reporting cannot convince financiers to reduce the cost of debt. In other words, in such an environment, increasing financial transparency is not only not an advantage. Still, it can also make companies' real risks more apparent, which in turn leads to an increase in the cost of debt.

Future Research Directions

In addition, the current study relied mainly on Altman's Z-score and SA indices to measure financial constraints. Future research could explore alternative measures of financial constraints (e.g., Kaplan–Zingales index, Whited–Wu index) to test the robustness of the findings. Moreover, incorporating macroeconomic variables such as inflation, exchange rate fluctuations, and interest rate shocks into the models could enrich the analysis, especially in volatile emerging economies like Iran. Extending the model to other emerging markets or unlisted and small-to-medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) would also enhance the generalizability of the results.

By integrating financial constraints into the relationship between FRQ and the cost of debt, this study opens a new line of inquiry in the literature on debt pricing in highly volatile economies. Future studies can build upon this framework by introducing broader measures, cross-country comparisons, and macroeconomic perspectives to provide deeper insights into how institutional and economic environments shape the reporting–financing nexus.

References

- Abad, D., Sánchez-Ballesta, J. P., & Yagüe, J. (2017). The short-term debt choice under asymmetric information. *SERIEs*, 8, 261-285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13209-017-0160-2>
- Abed, I. A., Hussin, N., Haddad, H., Almubaydeen, T. H., & Ali, M. A. (2022). Creative accounting determination and financial reporting quality: the integration of transparency and disclosure. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(1), 38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc8010038>
- Achek, I., & Gallali, M. I. (2015). Audit quality, timely disclosure, and the cost of debt: Tunisian evidence. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 11(4), 194-209. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17265/1548-6583/2015.04.002>

- Ahmad, M. M., Hunjra, A. I., & Taskin, D. (2023). Do asymmetric information and leverage affect investment decisions?. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 87, 337-345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2021.05.001>
- Ahmed, A. S., Billings, B. K., Morton, R. M., & Stanford-Harris, M. (2002). The role of accounting conservatism in mitigating bondholder-shareholder conflicts over dividend policy and in reducing debt costs. *The Accounting Review*, 77(4), 867-890. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2308/accr.2002.77.4.867>
- Ajina, A., Sougne, D., & Lakhal, F. (2015). Corporate disclosures, information asymmetry and stock-market liquidity in France. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 31(4), 1223. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jabr.v31i4.9297>
- Al-Hiyari, A., Kolsi, M. C., Lutfi, A., & Shakkour, A. S. (2024). Information asymmetry and dividend payout in an emerging market: Does corporate governance quality matter?. *Journal of open innovation: technology, market, and complexity*, 10(1), 100188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100188>
- Almeida, H., Campello, M., & Weisbach, M. S. (2004). The cash flow sensitivity of cash. *The journal of finance*, 59(4), 1777-1804. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.2004.00679.x>
- Altman, E. I. (1968). Financial ratios, discriminant analysis and the prediction of corporate bankruptcy. *The journal of finance*, 23(4), 589-609. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2978933>
- Amrah, M. R., & Hashim, H. A. (2020). The effect of financial reporting quality on the cost of debt: Sultanate of Oman evidence. *International Journal of Economics, Management and Accounting*, 28(2), 393-414. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijema.v28i2.749>
- Armstrong, C., Foster, G., & Taylor, D. (2016). Abnormal accruals in newly public companies: opportunistic misreporting or economic activity?. *Management Science*, 62(5), 1316-1338. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43835077>
- Ayagi, S. R., & Salisu, M. (2023). Financial reporting quality and information asymmetry: a review of empirical literature. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research [FUJAFR]*, 1(3), 19-29. <https://doi.org/10.33003/fujafir-2023.v1i3.51.19-29>
- Barclay, M. J., & Smith Jr, C. W. (1995). The maturity structure of corporate debt. *the Journal of Finance*, 50(2), 609-631. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1995.tb04797.x>
- Beatty, A., Liao, S., & Weber, J. (2010). The effect of private information and monitoring on the role of accounting quality in investment decisions. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 27(1), 17-47. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1911-3846.2010.01000.x>

- Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Maksimovic, V. (2008). Financing patterns around the world: Are small firms different?. *Journal of financial economics*, 89(3), 467-487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2007.10.005>
- Biddle, G. C., & Hilary, G. (2006). Accounting quality and firm-level capital investment. *The accounting review*, 81(5), 963-982. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr.2006.81.5.963>
- Biddle, G. C., Hilary, G., & Verdi, R. S. (2009). How does financial reporting quality relate to investment efficiency?. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 48(2-3), 112-131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2009.09.001>
- Biehl, H., Bleibtreu, C., & Stefani, U. (2024). The real effects of financial reporting: Evidence and suggestions for future research. *Journal of international accounting, auditing and taxation*, 54, 100594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intaccaudtax.2023.100594>
- Bracht, F., Mahieu, J., & Vanhaverbeke, S. (2024). The signaling value of legal form in entrepreneurial debt financing. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 39(3), 106380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2024.106380>
- Bushman, R. M., & Smith, A. J. (2001). Financial accounting information and corporate governance. *Journal of accounting and Economics*, 32(1-3), 237-333. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101\(01\)00027-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101(01)00027-1)
- Bushman, R. M., & Smith, A. J. (2003). Transparency, financial accounting information, and corporate governance. *Financial accounting information, and corporate governance. Economic Policy Review*, 9(1). <https://ssrn.com/abstract=795547>
- Cassar, G. (2004). The financing of business start-ups. *Journal of business venturing*, 19(2), 261-283. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(03\)00029-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(03)00029-6)
- Cathcart, L., Dufour, A., Rossi, L., & Varotto, S. (2020). The differential impact of leverage on the default risk of small and large firms. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 60, 101541. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2019.101541>
- Chen, B., Chen, W., & Yang, X. (2025). Does information asymmetry affect firm disclosure? Evidence from mergers and acquisitions of financial institutions. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 18(2), 64. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm18020064>
- Chen, T., Luo, W., & Xiang, X. (2022). Financial constraints, exchange rate changes and export price: Evidence from Chinese exporters. *Finance Research Letters*, 48, 102823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2022.102823>
- Ding, M., He, Z., Jia, Y., & Shen, M. (2021). State ownership, implicit government guarantees, and crash risk: Evidence from China. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 65, 101470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2020.101470>

- Ding, S., Liu, M., & Wu, Z. (2016). Financial reporting quality and external debt financing constraints: The case of privately held firms. *Abacus*, 52(3), 351-373. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/abac.12083>
- Ebrahimi, S. (2022). Financial constraint and output pricing: the case of international sanctions against Iran. *Journal of Applied Economics*, 25(1), 1219-1238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15140326.2022.2129145>
- Elahisahar, M., & Eskandar, H. (2017). The effect of financial reporting quality and debt maturity on different types of investment inefficiency. *Financial Accounting and Auditing Research*, 9(35), 95–120. (In Persian) <https://dorl.net/dor/20.1001.1.23830379.1396.9.35.5.4>
- Fazzari, S., Hubbard, R. G., & Petersen, B. (1988). Investment, financing decisions, and tax policy. *The American economic review*, 78(2), 200-205. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=227124>
- Figueroa, C., Iberti, G., Riutort, J., & Wagner, R. (2023). Do firms that state they are financially constrained tend to reinvest more of their profits?. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 90, 102902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.102902>
- Flannery, M. J. (1986). Asymmetric information and risky debt maturity choice. *The journal of finance*, 41(1), 19-37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.1986.tb04489.x>
- Francis, J., LaFond, R., Olsson, P., & Schipper, K. (2005). The market pricing of accruals quality. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 39(2), 295-327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2004.06.003>
- Fu, R., Kraft, A., & Zhang, H. (2012). Financial reporting frequency, information asymmetry, and the cost of equity. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 54(2-3), 132-149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2012.07.003>
- Gao, W., & Zhu, F. (2015). Information asymmetry and capital structure around the world. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 32, 131-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2015.01.005>
- Grossman, S. J., & Hart, O. D. (1986). The costs and benefits of ownership: A theory of vertical and lateral integration. *Journal of political economy*, 94(4), 691-719. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261404>
- Hadlock, C. J., & Pierce, J. R. (2010). New evidence on measuring financial constraints: Moving beyond the KZ index. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 23(5), 1909–1940. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhq009>
- Healy, P. M., & Palepu, K. G. (2001). Information asymmetry, corporate disclosure, and the capital markets: A review of the empirical disclosure literature. *Journal of*

accounting and economics, 31(1-3), 405-440. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-679X.2007.00238.x>

Ho, K. C., Sun, R., Yang, L., & Li, H. M. (2023). Information disclosure as a means of minimizing asymmetric financial reporting: The role of market reaction. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 78, 1221-1240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2023.04.022>

Hope, O. K., Thomas, W. B., & Vyas, D. (2013). Financial reporting quality of US private and public firms. *The Accounting Review*, 88(5), 1715-1742. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr-50494>

Hou, F., Shen, H., Wang, P., & Xiong, H. (2023). Signing auditors' cultural background and debt financing costs. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 87, 102617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.102617>

Hovakimian, G. (2011). Financial constraints and investment efficiency: Internal capital allocation across the business cycle. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 20(2), 264-283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2010.07.001>

Huong Dau, N., Van Nguyen, D., & Thi Thanh Diem, H. (2024). Annual report readability and firms' investment decisions. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 12(1), 2296230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2296230>

Jensen, M. C. & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the Firm. *Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure*, 3(4), 305-360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)

Jensen, M.C. (1986). Agency cost of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers. *The American Economic Review*, 76 (2), 323-329.

Kaplan, S. N., & Zingales, L. (1997). Do investment-cash flow sensitivities provide useful measures of financing constraints?. *The quarterly journal of economics*, 112(1), 169-215. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2951280>

Khan, M. A., Safdar, N., & Irfan, S. (2024). Role of financial constraints and risk-taking on the relationship between financial reporting quality and investment efficiency: emerging and frontier markets' perspective. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-12-2023-0779>

Kothari, S. P., Leone, A. J., & Wasley, C. E. (2005). Performance matched discretionary accrual measures. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 39(1), 163-197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2004.11.002>

Kurt, A. C. (2018). How do financial constraints relate to financial reporting quality? Evidence from seasoned equity offerings. *European Accounting Review*, 27(3), 527-557. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638180.2017.1279556>

- Lambert, R., Leuz, C., & Verrecchia, R. E. (2007). Accounting information, disclosure, and the cost of capital. *Journal of accounting research*, 45(2), 385-420. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-679X.2007.00238.x>
- Le, H. T. T., Vo, X. V., & Vo, T. T. (2021). Accruals quality and the cost of debt: Evidence from Vietnam. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 76, 101726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2021.101726>
- Leuz, C., & Verrecchia, R. E. (2005). Firms' capital allocation choices, information quality, and the cost of capital. *Information Quality, and the Cost of Capital (January 2005)*.
- Li, S., & Richie, N. (2016). Income smoothing and the cost of debt. *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 9(3), 175-190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjar.2016.03.001>
- Li, Z., Yu, Z., Yang, Z., & Ding, Z. (2025). Specialization in Bank Lending and short-term debt for long-term use: Evidence from China. *Finance Research Letters*, 75, 106825. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2025.106825>
- Martiny, A., Tagliatela, J., Testa, F., & Iraldo, F. (2024). Determinants of environmental social and governance (ESG) performance: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 456, 142213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142213>
- Mohammadi, Sh., & Moein Nezhad, B. (2015). The role of disclosure and transparency in financial reporting. *International Journal of Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 60-62. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijaes.v3i1.4549>
- Morellec, E., & Schürhoff, N. (2011). Corporate investment and financing under asymmetric information. *Journal of financial Economics*, 99(2), 262-288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2010.09.003>
- Neville, C., & Lucey, B. M. (2022). Financing Irish high-tech SMEs: The analysis of capital structure. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 83, 102219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2022.102219>
- Nikolov, B., Schmid, L., & Steri, R. (2021). The sources of financing constraints. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 139(2), 478-501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2020.07.018>
- Rahban, A., Ghahramani, A., Yusefzadeh, H., Harirchi, I., & Alinia, C. (2024). Price transparency in Iranian healthcare market. *Health Policy OPEN*, 100120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hpopen.2024.100120>
- Rapposelli, A., Birindelli, G., & Modina, M. (2024). The relationship between firm size and efficiency: why does default on bank loans matter?. *Quality & Quantity*, 58(4), 3379-3401. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-023-01810-9>

- Roszkowska-Menkes, M., Aluchna, M., & Kamiński, B. (2024). True transparency or mere decoupling? The study of selective disclosure in sustainability reporting. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 98, 102700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpa.2023.102700>
- Saghafi, A., & Arabmazar Yazdi, M. (2010). Financial reporting quality and investment inefficiency. *Journal of Financial Accounting Research*, 2(4), 1–20. (In Persian) <https://dor.isc.ac/dor/20.1001.1.23223405.1389.2.4.1.9>
- Shemshad, A., & Imeni, M. (2022). Cash holding, firm value and performance under financial constraint: a case study of the Iranian Capital Market. *Innovation management and operational strategies*, 2(4), 434-446. (in Persian) <https://doi.org/10.22105/imos.2021.314356.1184>
- Szarzec, K., Dombi, Á., & Matuszak, P. (2021). State-owned enterprises and economic growth: Evidence from the post-Lehman period. *Economic Modelling*, 99, 105490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2021.03.009>
- Tuğsal Doruk, Ö., & Martial Gohore, B. I. C. (2024). A Financing Constraints Paradox? Internal Finance and Capital Structure Link for Tourism Firms: Asian Emerging Market evidence. *SAGE Open*, 14(4), 21582440241265305. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241265305>
- Valta, P. (2012). Competition and the cost of debt. *Journal of financial economics*, 105(3), 661-682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2012.04.004>
- Van, V. T. T., Dang Ngoc, H., Nguyen Ngoc, T., & Anh Le, H. (2022). Earnings quality and the cost of debt: A case study of Vietnam. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2140489. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2140489>
- Vander Bauwhede, H., De Meyere, M., & Van Cauwenberge, P. (2015). Financial reporting quality and the cost of debt of SMEs. *Small Business Economics*, 45, 149-164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-015-9645-1>
- Verdi, R. S. (2006). Financial reporting quality and investment efficiency. Available at SSRN: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.930922>
- Vihriälä, E. (2023). Self-imposed liquidity constraints via voluntary debt repayment. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 150(2), 103708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2023.103708>
- Zhou, H., Maneesoonthorn, W. O., & Chen, X. B. (2021). The predictive ability of quarterly financial statements. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 9(3), 50. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs9030050>

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2026 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license logo, showing the CC symbol and a person icon with the letters 'BY' below it.
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Imeni, M. and Parvizi, M. (2026). Financial Reporting Quality on the Cost of Debt with Emphasis on the Role of Financial Constraints in Iran. (e241969). <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 13(3), 270-293. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.526171.1781</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_241969.html</p>	A square QR code that, when scanned, likely leads to the full article page on the journal's website.